

Advanced software stack for Earth system data

Deliverable D4.1

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Abstract

An exascale simulation requires extreme-scale I/O. Existing workflows will not scale to this extent, particularly as an exascale simulation is likely to involve a smaller number of individuals carrying out large simulations and a larger number of individuals carrying out analysis of simulation products. Such analysis is bound to include data comparison from simulations carried out in multiple locations and stored on a range of media.

ESiWACE addresses the entire workflow with software solutions addressing a range of targets, from simulation, through analysis, to information management across institutions. Most of the effort has been devoted to the simulation problem with work on both improving I/O from simulations (using the Earth System Data Middleware, ESDM) and on ensemble data analysis (using the X I/O server, XIOS).

The ESDM provides relaxed I/O semantics and manages the heterogeneous storage available in a data centre by mapping datasets dynamically to (possibly multiple) storage locations, addressing both simulation and analysis use cases. This document provides a high-level descriptions of that software stack, including full documentation and information about how to enable ESDM support for existing NetCDF applications and utilise the ESDM API for software development.

As part of the development that resulted in the ESDM architecture described and documented here, the ESDM code was hardened, and the I/O path has been investigated for many use cases and optimised. The performance measurements indicate that performance can be close to optimal for large-scale data access. Several additional features had been explored and prototyped that bear a high potential for large-scale performance improvements and co-design with vendors. These include new storage backends for S3, Motr, KOVE, PMEM-IO, and IME, which have been developed to bypass the POSIX API and accelerate performance.

Ensemble data analysis can be carried out using existing tools (CYLC and XIOS), albeit with customisations that are model dependent. The necessary software can be built using NetCDF directly, or with the ESDM.

Conclusion & Results

The further development, testing, and hardening of the ESDM I/O library has yielded software which could provide a significant legacy from ESiWACE2. Performance tests show a significant improvement compared to existing NetCDF implementations. The implementation of ESDM interfaces in other popular programming languages makes ESDM accessible to a broad audience and will support the dissemination of ESDM (at the moment, ESDM supports the programming languages C, and C++ directly and Python and Fortran via a modified NetCDF stack). ESDM backends include a range of systems (including both public interfaces such as POSIX and S3 and private interfaces such as DDN's WOS and IME).

Optimisations include localising and parallelising critical parts of code and integrating effective performance features, particularly, CopyOnWrite and lossless and lossy compression¹. The CopyOnWrite feature that can significantly reduce resource consumption for read-intensive applications and lossless and lossy compression can save storage space and reduce network overhead.

The documentation was re-worked and improved to make a quick start easier for new users and developers. It is available in PDF, HTML and Markdown formats, contains many examples, and is available online on Github².

One fully worked use case is explored in this deliverable, the use of the ESDM within Ophidia. Other use cases will be explored during the remainder of this project.

¹<https://github.com/JulianKunkel/scil>

²<https://github.com/ESiWACE/esdm>

XIOS ensemble data analysis results suggest the technique will deliver ensemble statistics with very marginal overheads on run-time (and thus very significant reductions in time over the entire workflow).

Project Objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to the achievement of all the macro-objectives and specific goals:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable
(1) Enable leading European weather and climate models to leverage pre-exascale systems' available performance concerning both compute and data capacity in 2021.	X
(2) Prepare the weather and climate community to make use of exascale systems when they become available.	X
Specific goals in the workplan	Contribution of this deliverable
Boost European climate and weather models to operate in world-leading quality on existing supercomputing and future pre-exascale platforms.	X
Establish new technologies for weather and climate modelling.	X
Enhance HPC capacity of the weather and climate community.	-
Improve the toolchain to manage data from climate and weather simulations at scale.	X
Strengthen the interaction with the European HPC ecosystem.	X
Foster co-design between model developers, HPC manufacturers and HPC centres.	X

Contents

1	ESDM Design	7
1.1	Data model	7
1.1.1	Conceptual Data Model	7
1.1.2	Logical Data Model	8
1.2	Supported Data Backends	10
1.2.1	DDN Web Object Scaler (WOS)	11
1.2.2	DDN Infinite Memory Engine (IME)	11
1.2.3	Seagate Motr (MOTR)	11
1.2.4	Portable Operating System Interface (POSIX)	11
1.2.5	Kove Direct System Architecture (KDSA)	11
1.2.6	Amazon Simple Storage Service (S3)	12
2	ESDM User Guide	12
2.1	Documentation	12
2.1.1	PDF	12
2.1.2	Github-Markdown	12
2.1.3	HTML and Latex with API reference	13
2.2	Building instructions	13
2.2.1	Dependencies (Spack)	13
2.2.2	ESDM prototype	14
2.2.3	ESDM-NetCDF and ESDM-NetCDF-Python	14
2.2.4	Docker	15
2.3	Configuration	15
2.3.1	Search paths	16
2.3.2	File format	16
2.3.3	Data parameters	16
2.3.4	Metadata Parameters	21
2.4	Usage	22
2.4.1	NetCDF	22
2.4.2	CDO	23
2.4.3	XIOS	23
2.4.4	Python	24
2.4.5	Dask	25
2.4.6	NetCDF-Bench	25
2.4.7	Paraview	25
3	ESDM Developer Guide	25
3.1	Internal Data Model	26
3.1.1	Dataspace	26
3.1.2	Dataset	27
3.1.3	Container	28
3.1.4	Grid	28
3.2	Usage examples	29
3.2.1	Basic writing	29
3.2.2	Grid-based writing	30
3.2.3	Simple reading	30
3.2.4	Grid-based reading	31

4 ESDM Performance Measurement	32
4.1 NetCDF-Bench	32
4.2 Shallow-Water-Equations	32
5 An example ESDM use case: Ophidia	36
5.1 Integration of the Ophidia framework with ESDM	36
5.2 Integration through the ESDM-NetCDF library	36
5.3 Direct integration through the ESDM library	38
6 Ensemble Analysis and Data Reduction using XIOS	39
6.1 Data reduction	39
6.2 Ensemble workflow resilience	40
7 Sustainability	44
8 How this deliverable contributes to the European HPC strategies	44
9 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any	44
9.1 Lessons learned	45
10 Dissemination, Engagement and Uptake of Results	45
10.1 Target audience	45
10.2 Record of dissemination/engagement activities linked to this deliverable	45
10.3 Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable	45

1 ESDM Design

The ESDM implements the architecture discussed in [9, 3], which main purpose is to distribute metadata and data on multiple-storage tiers hiding the complexity from end-users. The design defines implementation details such as data model and includes side activities such as testing procedures, backend support and documentation.

The design and related activities were distributed fairly between the institutes. UoR contributed to the data model and testing of storage backends. The DKRZ developers hardened the prototype, conducted NetCDF-ESDM benchmarks, developed and tested the GRID-API, and wrote documentation.

1.1 Data model

The data model of a system organizes elements of data, standardizes how they represent data entities and how users can interact with the data. The **model** can be split into three layers:

- The **conceptual data** model describes the entities and the semantics of the domain that are represented by the data model and the typical operations to manipulate the data. In our case, the scientific domain is numerical weather prediction and climate.
- The **logical data model** describes the abstraction level provided by the system, how domain entities are mapped to objects provided by the system³, and the supported operations to access and manipulate these objects are defined. Importantly, the **logical data model** defines the semantics when using the operations to access and manipulate the system objects. For example, a system object of a relational model is a table – representing attributes of a set of objects – and a row of a table representing attributes of a single object.
- The **physical data model** describes how the logical entities are finally mapped to objects/files/regions on available hardware. The physical data model is partly covered by the backends of ESDM, therefore, the descriptions will stop at that abstraction level.

1.1.1 Conceptual Data Model

Our conceptual data model is aligned with the needs of domain scientists from climate and weather. It reuses and extends from concepts introduced in a data model proposed for the Climate and Forecasting conventions for NetCDF data [7].

Variable: A variable, V , defines a set of data representing a discrete (generally scalar) quantity discretised within a “sampling” domain, d . It is accompanied by metadata.

Metadata: Which will include at the minimum, a name, but may also include units, and information about additional dimensionality, directly (e.g. via a key, value pair such as that necessary to expose $z = 1.5m$ for air temperature at 1.5m) or indirectly (e.g. via pointers to other generic coordinate variables which describe the sampled domain). There may also be a dictionary of additional metadata which may or may not conform to an external semantic convention or standard. Such metadata could include information about the tool used to observe or simulate the specific variable. Additional metadata is also required for all the other entities described below.

Dimension: The sampling domain d is defined by dimensions which define an a coordinate axis. Dimensions will also include metadata, which must again, include at a minimum a name (e.g. height, time), but may also include information about directionality, units (e.g. degrees, months, days-since-a-particular-time-using-a-particular-calendar), or details of how to construct an algorithm to find the actual sampling coordinates, perhaps using a well known algorithm such as an ISO 8601 time.

³A entity of the domain model such as a car could be mapped to one or several objects.

Coordinate: Coordinates are the set of values at which data is sampled along any given dimension. They may be explicitly defined by indexing into a coordinate variable, or implicitly defined by an algorithm. When we talk about the coordinates, it is usually clear if we mean the N-dimensional coordinate to address data in a given variable or if we just mean the (1D) coordinate along one dimension.

Cell: The data values are known at points, which may or may not represent a cell. Such cells are n-dimensional shapes where the dimensionality may or may not fully encompass the dimensionality of the domain. n-dimensional shapes can be implicitly defined in which case the Cartesian product of all dimensional coordinates forms the data "cube" of the cell, but they can also be explicitly defined, either by providing bounds on the coordinate variables (via metadata) or by introducing a new variable which explicitly defines the functional boundaries of the cell (as might happen in a finite element unstructured grid).

Dataset: Variables can be aggregated into datasets. A dataset contains multiple variables that logically belong together, and should be associated with metadata describing the reason for the aggregation. Variables must have unique names within a dataset.

Our conceptual model assumes that all variables are scalars, but clearly to make use of these scalars requires more complex interpretation. In particular, we need to know the datatype and operators.

Datatype: defines the types of values that are valid and the operations that can be conducted. While we are mostly dealing with scalars, they may not be amenable to interpretation as simple numbers. For example, a variable may be storing an integer which points into a taxonomy of categories of land-surface-types. More complex structures could include complex data types such as vectors, compressed ensemble values, or structures within this system, provided such interpretation is handled outside of the ESDM, and documented in metadata. This allows us to limit ourselves to simple data types plus arbitrary length blocks of bits.

Operators: define the manipulations possible on the conceptual entities. The simplest operators will include creation, read, update and delete applied to an entity as a whole, or to a subset, however even these simple operators will come with constraints, for example, it should not be possible to delete a coordinate variable without deleting the parent variable as well. There will need to be a separation of concerns between operators which can be handled within the ESDM subsystem, and those which require external logic. Operators which might require external logic could include subsetting — it will be seen that the ESDM will support simple subsetting using simple coordinates — but complex subsets such as finding a region in real space from dimensions spanned using an algorithm or coordinate variable, may require knowledge of how such algorithms or variables are specified. Such knowledge is embedded in conventions such as the CF NetCDF conventions, and this knowledge could only be provided to the ESDM via appropriate operator plugins.

1.1.2 Logical Data Model

The logical data model describes how data is represented inside ESDM, the operations to interact with the data and their semantics. There are four first class entities in the ESDM logical data model: **variables**, **fragments**, **containers**, and **metadata**. ESDM entities may be linked by ESDM **references**, and a key property which emerges from the use of references is that no ESDM entity instance may be deleted while references to it still exist. The use of reference counting will ensure this property as well as avoid dangling pointers.

Each of these entities is now described, along with a list of supported operations:

Variable: In the logical data model, the variable corresponds directly to a variable in the conceptual data model. Each element of the variable sampled across the dimensions contains data with a prescribed **DataType**. Variables are associated with both **Scientific Metadata** and **Technical Metadata**. Variables are partitioned

into **fragments** each of which can be stored on one or more “storage backend”. A variable definition includes internal information about the domain (bounding box in some coordinate system) and dimensionality (size and shape), while the detailed information about which coordinate variables are needed to span the dimensions and how they are defined is held in the technical metadata. Similarly, where a variable is itself a coordinate variable, a link to the parent variable for which it is used is held in the technical metadata. The ESDM will not allow an attempt to delete a variable to succeed while any such references exist (see references). A key part of the variable definition is the list of fragments associated with it, and if possible, how they are organised to span the domain. Users may choose to submit code pieces that are then run within the I/O-path (not part within ESiWACE implementation), such an operation covers the typical filter, map and reduce operations of the data flow programming paradigm.

Fragments are created by the backend while appending/modifying data to a variable.

Operations:

- Variables can be created and deleted.
- Fragments of data can be attached and deleted.
- Fragments can be repartitioned and reshuffled.
- Integrity can be checked.
- Data can be read, appended or modified those operations will be translated to the responsible fragments.
- Metadata can be atomically attached to a variable or modified.
- A variable can be sealed to make it immutable for all subsequent modifications.
- Process data of the variable somewhere in the I/O-path.

Fragment: A fragment is a piece (subdomain) of a variable. The ESDM expects to handle fragments as atomic entities, that is, only one process can write a fragment through the ESDM, and the ESDM will write fragments as atomic entities to storage backends. The backends are free to further partition these fragments in an appropriate way, for example, by sharding using chunks as described in the mapping section. However, the ESDM is free to replicate fragments or subsets of fragments and to choose which backend is appropriate for any given fragment. This allows, for example, the ESDM to split a variable into fragments some of which are on stored on a parallel file system, while others are placed in object storage.

Operations:

- Data of fragments can be read, appended or modified.
- Integrity of the fragment can be checked.
- Process data of the variable somewhere in the I/O-path.

Container: A container is a virtual entity providing views on collections of variables, allowing multiple different datasets (as defined in the conceptual model) to be realised over the variables visible to the ESDM. Each container provides a hierarchical namespace holding references to one or multiple variables together with metadata. Variables cannot be deleted while they are referenced by a container. The use of these dynamic containers provides support for much more flexible organisation of data than provided by a regular file system semantics — and efficiently support high level applications such as the Data Reference Syntax [13].

A container provides the ESDM storage abstraction which is analogous to an external file. Because many scientific metadata conventions are based on semantic structures which span variables within a file in ways that may be opaque to the ESDM without the use of a plugin, the use of a container can indicate to the ESDM that these variables are linked even though the ESDM does not understand why, and so they cannot be independently deleted. When entire files in NetCDF format are ingested into the ESDM, the respective importing tool must create a container to ensure such linking properties are not lost.

Operations:

- Creation and deletion of containers.
- Creation and deletion of names in the hierarchical name space; the creation of links to an existing variable.
- Attaching and modification of metadata.
- Integrity can be checked.

Metadata: Can be associated with all the other first class entities (variables, fragments, and containers). Such metadata is split into internal ESDM technical metadata, and external user-supplied semantic metadata.

Technical metadata covers, e.g., permissions, information about data location and timestamps. A backend will be able to add its own metadata to provide the information to lookup the data for the fragment from the storage backend managed by it. Metadata by itself is treated like a normal ESDM variable but linked to the variable of choice. The implementation may embed (simple) metadata into fragments of original data (see Reference).

Operations:

- Users can create, read, or delete arbitrary scientific metadata onto variables and containers. A future version of the ESDM may support user scientific metadata for fragments.
- Container level metadata is generally not directly associated with variables, but may be retrieved via following references from variables to containers.
- Queries allow to search for arbitrary metadata, e.g., for objects that have (`experiment=X`, `model=Y`, `time=yesterday`) returning the variables and containers in a list that match. This enables to locate scientific data in an arbitrary namespace.

Reference: A reference is a link between entities and can be used in many places, references can be embedded instead of real data of these logical objects. For example, dimensions inside a variable can be references, also a container typically uses references to variables.

Operations:

- A reference can be created from existing logical entities or removed.

Namespace: ESDM does not offer a simple hierarchical namespace for the files. It provides the elementary functions to navigate the data space derived from human interaction with the world: *teleportation*⁴ and *orientation*⁵ in the following fashion: Queries about semantical data properties (e.g., `experiment=myExperiment`, `model=myModel`, `date=yesterday`) can be performed returning a list of matching files with their respective metadata. Iterating the list (*orientation*) is similar to listing a directory in a file system.

Note that this reduces the burden to define a hierarchical namespace and for data sharing services based on scientific metadata. An input/output container for an application can be assembled on-the-fly by using queries and naming the resulting entities. As a container provides a hierarchical namespace, by harnessing this capability one can search for relevant variables and map them into the local file system tree, accessing these variables as if they would be, e.g., NetCDF files. By offering a FUSE client, this feature also enables backwards compatibility for legacy POSIX applications.

1.2 Supported Data Backends

ESDM uses at least one storage backends but can use multiple to store the data and exactly one metadata backend.

⁴Instantaneous travel to a location based on data properties, e.g., using a search query.

⁵Browsing to data related to the current location.

1.2.1 DDN Web Object Scaler (WOS)

DDN's Web Object Scaler or WOS is a distributed object storage system designed for extremely large data. It is available as a complete hardware/software solution or can be deployed on third-party hardware. Although, the nodes can be geographically distributed, they present a shared pool for object storage. The data can be accessed over HTTP/REST, WebDAV, Swift, and S3 interfaces. Additionally, the pools can be mounted via NFS and CIFS/SMB.

1.2.2 DDN Infinite Memory Engine (IME)

IME is a scale-out, software-defined, flash Cache Layer using NVMe SSDs inserted between compute cluster and Parallel File System. It includes a server and a client component: rather than issuing I/O to a parallel file system client, the IME client intercepts the I/O fragments and issues these to the IME server layer which manages the NVM media and stores and protects the data. Prior to synchronizing the data to the backing file system, IME coalesces and aligns the I/O optimally for the file system. The read case works in the reverse: file data is ingested into the cache efficiently in parallel across the IME server layer and will satisfy reads from here in fragments according to the read request. IME manages at-scale flash to eliminate file system bottlenecks and the burden of creating and maintaining application-specific optimizations. It delivers:

- New levels of I/O performance for predictable job completion in even the most demanding and complex high-performance environments.
- Performance scaling independent of storage capacity for system designs with order of magnitude reductions in hardware.
- Application transparency that eliminates the need to create and maintain application-specific optimizations.

1.2.3 Seagate Motr (MOTR)

Motr is an object storage system developed by Seagate to overcome typical limitations of traditional storage systems. In contrast to similar I/O storage systems (e.g. Ceph and DAOS), Motr accesses raw block devices directly.

The design of Motr supports raw data and metadata. To achieve that it offers two types of objects: (1) A common object which is an array of fixed-size of blocks. Data can be read from and written to these objects. (2) An index for a key-value store. Key-value records can be put to and get from an index. At the moment, Motr provides a C interface.

1.2.4 Portable Operating System Interface (POSIX)

The Portable Operating System Interface (POSIX) is a family of standards specified by the IEEE Computer Society for maintaining compatibility between operating systems. POSIX defines the application programming interface (API), along with command line shells and utility interfaces, for software compatibility with variants of Unix and other operating systems.

1.2.5 Kove Direct System Architecture (KDSA)

Kove External Memory [8] allows the CPU access to unlimited memory right below the CPU cache. Any data set can live in memory, close to the core, reducing processing time. The KDSA API is a low-level API that allows to access data on external memory by utilizing RDMA. Data can be transferred synchronously or asynchronously, additionally, memory can be pre-registered for use with the Infiniband HCA. Since registration of memory is time consuming, for unregistered memory regions the system may either use an internal (pre-registered) buffer and copy the user's data to the buffer, or for larger accesses it registers the memory, performs an RDMA data transfer and then unregisters the memory again.

1.2.6 Amazon Simple Storage Service (S3)

Amazon Simple Storage Service (S3) is a scalable, web-based, high-speed cloud storage service with a simple-to-use API. The service allows saving and archiving of data reliably in the Amazon Web Services (AWS) of all sizes. It is suitable for use cases, like backup, archives, big-data, IoT devices, websites and much more.

2 ESDM User Guide

The end-user guide in this section describes installation, configuration, and usage of ESDM.

2.1 Documentation

Figure 1: Conversion paths.

The documentation is organized as a set of latex and resource files. This structure simplifies integration in other documents if only particular documentation parts are required. The source files are located in `./doc/latex`. This is a central location where files can be modified if changes are required. All other locations listed in these sections are auto-generated. Therefore, after recompilation all changes will be overwritten.

Documentation centralization reduces documentation efforts. Changes in the latex files will affect all other auto-generated documents. As shown in Figure 1, the latex source files are exported to PDF, Github-Markdown, Latex and HTML formats. PDF and Github-Markdown don't include ESDM-API reference which is found in the Latex and HTML generated by Doxygen.

The Listings 1 to 5 in this section assume that current working directory is the ESDM repository. The subsections discuss the supported export possibilities in detail.

2.1.1 PDF

Latex documentation can be compiled to a PDF file by commands shown in Listing 1. The result will be stored in `./doc/latex/main.pdf`

```
cd ./doc
make
```

Listing 1: Make PDF document

2.1.2 Github-Markdown

The Github documentation `./README.md` is generated by `pandoc` from the `./doc/latex/main.tex` file. `./README.md` should never be modified manually since the next documentation compilation will overwrite changes. The compilation commands are shown in Listing 2.

```
cd ./doc
make
```

Listing 2: Make ./README.md

2.1.3 HTML and Latex with API reference

Doxygen depends on a set of auto-generated markdown files, which should never be modified manually because the next compilation will overwrite all changes. Please always work with files in `./doc/latex` folder and compile them running the make script as shown in Listing 3.

```
cd ./doc
make
```

Listing 3: Markdown files generation

The resulting `*.md` files are generated in `./doc/markdown` directory. Now all required source files for Doxygen should be available, and the final documentation can be compiled by `doxygen` as shown in Listing 4.

```
./configure
cd build
doxygen
```

Listing 4: Make HTML and Latex documents

The resulting HTML start page is located in `./build/doc/html/index.html`, and the main Latex document is located in `./build/doc/latex/refman.tex`.

```
cd doc/latex
pdflatex refman.tex
```

Listing 5: Comple PDF with API reference

The resulting PDF file is `./build/doc/latex/refman.pdf`

2.2 Building instructions

This guide documents installation procedures to build prerequisites as well as the prototype codebase for development and testing purposes.

2.2.1 Dependencies (Spack)

Although the software trees on supercomputer may provide all the standard tools and libraries required to build ESDM, it is still recommended to build, install, and manage dependencies via Spack⁶. The instructions below show how to setup Spack and install the ESDM dependencies.

1. Download and enable Spack

```
git clone --depth=2 https://github.com/spack/spack.git spack
. spack/share/spack/setup-env.sh
```

2. Set a `gcc` version to be used

```
gccver=7.3.0
```

3. Install dependencies

```
spack install gcc@$gccver +binutils
spack compiler find
spack install autoconf@gcc@$gccver
spack install openmpi@gcc@$gccver gettext@gcc@$gccver
spack install jansson@gcc@$gccver glib@gcc@$gccver
```

⁶<https://spack.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html>

Figure 2: Dependencies overview

4. Load dependencies

```

spack load gcc@$gccver
spack load -r autoconf@gcc@$gccver
spack load -r libtool@gcc@$gccver
spack load -r openmpi@gcc@$gccver
spack load -r jansson@gcc@$gccver
spack load -r glib@gcc@$gccver

```

2.2.2 ESDM prototype

Assuming all prerequisites have been installed and tested, ESDM can be configured and build as follows.

1. Ensure environment is aware of dependencies installed using [spack](#) and [dev-env](#)

```
git clone https://github.com/ESiWACE/esdm
```

2. Configure and build ESDM

```

cd esdm
pushd deps
./prepare.sh
popd
./configure \
  --prefix=${PREFIX} \
  --enable-netcdf4
cd build
make
make install

```

2.2.3 ESDM-NetCDF and ESDM-NetCDF-Python

1. Clone the NetCDF-ESDM repository

```
git clone https://github.com/ESiWACE/esdm-netcdf-c
```

2. Configure and build NetCDF-ESDM. (`$INSTPATH` is the installation path of ESDM.)

```

cd esdm-netcdf-c
/bootstrap
./configure \
  --prefix=$prefix \
  --with-esdm=$INSTPATH \

```

```
LD_FLAGS="-L$INSTPATH/lib" \
CFLAGS="-I$INSTPATH/include" \
CC=mpicc \
--disable-dap
make -j
make install
```

3. If required, install the netcdf4-python module. Change to the ESDM-NetCDF repository's root directory and install the patched NetCDF-Python module.

```
cd dev
git clone https://github.com/Unidata/netcdf4-python.git
cd netcdf4-python
patch -s -p1 < ../v2.patch
python3 setup.py install --user
```

2.2.4 Docker

For the development of ESDM, the directory `./dev/docker` contains all requirements to set up a development environment using docker quickly. The Docker files contain ESDM installation instructions for different distributions. For easy building Docker files for different platforms are provided in different flavours:

- CentOS/Fedora/RHEL like systems
- Ubuntu/Debian like systems

Setup Assuming the docker service is running you can build the docker images as follows:

```
cd ./dev/docker
cd <choose ubuntu/fedora/..>
sudo docker build -t esdm .
```

After docker is done building an image, you should see the ESDM test suite's output, which verifies that the development environment is set up correctly. The output should look similar to the following output:

```
Running tests...
Test project /data/esdm/build
Start 1: metadata
1/2 Test #1: metadata ..... Passed    0.00 sec
Start 2: readwrite
2/2 Test #2: readwrite ..... Passed    0.00 sec

100% tests passed, 0 tests failed out of 2

Total Test time (real) =  0.01 sec
```

Usage Running the ESDM Docker container will run the test suite:

```
sudo docker run esdm # should display test output
```

You can also explore the development environment interactively:

```
sudo docker run -it esdm bash
```

```
docker run dev/docker/ubuntu-whole-stack/Dockerfile
```

2.3 Configuration

ESDM can store metadata and data separately. Furthermore, the data can be distributed over multiple storage media. How exactly the data is distributed can be specified in the configuration file. This section describes the file structure, the metadata and supported storage backends configuration and provides examples.

2.3.1 Search paths

The current implementation reads `esdm.conf` file in the current directory. In the next ESDM versions it is planned to support other common paths as well, like `/etc/esdm/esdm.conf`, `~/.config/esdm/esdm.conf`, `~/.esdm.conf`, `./esdm.conf`. In addition, the configuration should also be possible via the environment variable and arguments.

2.3.2 File format

The configuration file format is based on JSON, i.e. all configuration files must be valid JSON files. However, ESDM places some restrictions on what keys are recognized and which types are expected. The tables summarize parameters that can be used in the configuration file. Parameters can be of four types: string, integer, float and object, which are collections of key-value pairs.

The `"esdm": {}` key-value pair in the root of the JSON configuration file can contain configuration for multiple data backends and one metadata backend. The backends are organized in the `"backends": []` key-value pair as a list.

```
{
  "esdm": {
    "backends": [
      <insert backend config here>,
      <insert backend config here>,
      ...
      <insert backend config here>,
    "metadata": {
      <insert metadata config here>,
    }
  }
}
```

2.3.3 Data parameters

Parameter	Type	Default		Description
id	string	(not set)	required	Unique identifier
type	string	(not set)	required	Backend name
target	string	(not set)	required	Connection specification (Bucket name for S3)
performance-model	object	(not set)	optional	Performance model definition.
max-threads-per-node	integer	0	optional	Maximum number of threads on a node.
write-stream-blocksize	integer	0	optional	Blocksize in bytes used to write fragments.
max-global-threads	integer	0	optional	Maximum total number of threads.
accessibility	string	global	optional	Data access permission rights.
max-fragment-size	integer	10485760	optional	Maximum fragment size in bytes.
fragmentation-method	string	contiguous	optional	Fragmentation methods.

Table 1: Backend configuration parameters overview

Parameter: `/esdm/backends/id` Unique alpha-numeric identifier.

Type string
 Default (not set)
 Required yes

Parameter: /esdm/backends/type Storage backend type.

Type string
 Default (not set)
 Required yes

Can take a value of one of the supported backends.

Type	Description
MOTR	Seagate Object Storage API
DUMMY	Dummy storage (Used for development)
IME	DDN Infinite Memory Engine
KDSA	Kove Direct System Architecture
POSIX	Portable Operating System Interface
S3	Amazon Simple Storage Service
WOS	DDN Web Object Scaler

Parameter: /esdm/backends/target The target specifies connection to storage. Therefore, its value depends on the storage type. The following sections describe targets for each storage type and provide an example.

Type string
 Default (not set)
 Required yes

Type = MOTR

If Seagate Object Storage API is selected, then the target string is composed of four parameters separated by spaces.

```
[local_addr] [ha_addr] [prof] [proc_fid]
```

where

- "local_addr" is the local address used to connect to Motr service,
- "ha_addr" is the hardware address in Motr service,
- "prof" is the profile FID in the Motr service, and
- "proc_fid" is the process FID in the Motr service.

```
{
  "type": "MOTR",
  "id": "c1",
  "target": " :12345:33:103 192.168.168.146@tcp:12345:34:1
<0x7000000000000001:0> <0x7200000000000001:64>"
}
```

Type = DUMMY

Used for development.

```
{
  "type": "DUMMY",
  "id": "c1",
  "target": " ./_dummy",
}
```

Type = IME

The target is the IME storage mount point.

```
{
  "type": "IME",
  "id": "p1",
  "target": "./_ime"
}
```

Type = KDSA

Prefix “xpd:” followed by volume specifications. Multiple volume names can be connected by “+” sign.

```
xpd:mlx5\_0.1/260535867639876.9:e58c053d-ac6b-4973-9722-cf932843fe4e[+mlx...]
```

A module specification consists of several parts. The caller provides a device handle, the target serial number, the target link number, and the volume UUID. The convention for specifying a KDSA volume uses the following format:

```
[localdevice[.localport]/][serialnumber[.linknum]:]volumeid
```

where the square brackets indicate optional parts of the volume connection specification. Thus, a volumeid is nominally sufficient to specify a desired volume; one can then optionally additionally specify the serial number of the XPD with optional link number and/or the local device to use with optional local port number. The convention for specifying multiple KDSA volumes to stripe together uses the following format:

```
volume_specifier[+volume_specifier[+volume_specifier[+...]]][@parameter]
```

where the square brackets indicate optional parts of the aggregated connection specification. Thus, a single volume connection specification is sufficient for a full connection specifier, and one can then optionally specify additional volume specifiers to aggregate, using the plus sign as a separator. The user may also additionally specify parameters for the aggregation, using the “at sign”, a single character as a parameter identifier, and the parameter value.

```
{
  "type": "KDSA",
  "id": "p1",
  "target": "This is the XPD connection string",
}
```

Type = POSIX

The target string is the path to a directory.

```
{
  "type": "POSIX",
  "id": "p2",
  "target": "./_posix2"
}
```

Type = S3

The target string is a bucket name with at least a 5 characters. A proper S3 configuration requires at three additional parameters: [host](#), [secret-key](#) and [access-key](#). Other parameters are optional.

Parameter	Type	Default		Description
host	string	(not set)	required	A valid endpoint name for the Amazon S3 region provided by the agency.
secret-key	string	(not set)	required	Secret Access Key for the account.
access-key	string	(not set)	required	Access key ID for the account.
locationConstraint	string	(not set)	optional	Specifies the Region where the bucket will be created. If you don't specify a Region, the bucket is created in the US East (N. Virginia) Region (us-east-1). For a list of all the Amazon S3 supported regions, see API Bucket reference (https://docs.aws.amazon.com/AmazonS3/latest/API/API_CreateBucket.html)
authRegion	string	(not set)	optional	For a list of all the Amazon S3 supported regions and endpoints, see regions and endpoints in the AWS General Reference (https://docs.aws.amazon.com/general/latest/gr/rande.html#s3_region)
timeout	integer	(not set)	optional	Request timeout in milliseconds.
s3-compatible	integer	(not set)	optional	Flag for LibS3
use-ssl	integer	0	optional	Use HTTPS for encryption, if enabled.

```
{
  "type": "S3",
  "id": "p1",
  "target": "._posix1",
  "access-key": "",
  "secret-key": "",
  "host": "localhost:9000"
}
```

Type = WOS

The target string is a concatenation of `key=value;` pairs. The `host` key specifies the WOS service host. The `policy` name is that one, that was set up on the DDN WOS console.

```
{
  "type": "WOS",
  "id": "w1",
  "target": "host=192.168.80.33;policy=test;"
}
```

Parameter: performance-model The performance model estimates expected performance of backends and can affect the choice of backend.

Type object
 Default (not set)
 Required no

Dynamic performance model parameters.

Parameter	Type	Default	Domain		Description
latency	float	0.0	≥ 0.0	optional	Latency in seconds
throughput	float	0.0	> 0.0	optional	Throughput in MiB/s

Generic performance model parameters. The proximity coefficient determines how fast the performance model reacts to backend performance fluctuations. The higher the value, the faster the performance estimation.

Parameter	Type	Default	Domain		Description
latency	float	0.0	≥ 0.0	optional	Latency in seconds
throughput	float	0.0	> 0.0	optional	Throughput in MiB/s
size	integer	0	> 0	optional	Test buffer size in bytes

Parameter	Type	Default	Domain		Description
period	float	0.0	> 0.0	optional	Test period in seconds
alpha	float	0.0	[0.0, 1.0)	optional	Adaption rate

Parameter: max-threads-per-node Maximum number of threads on a node. If `max-threads-per-node=0`, then the ESDM scheduler estimates an optimal value.

Type integer
 Default 0
 Required no

Parameter: write-stream-blocksize Block size in bytes used to read/write fragments. If `write-stream-blocksize=0`, then ESDM estimates optimal block size for each storage type individually.

Type integer
 Default 0
 Required no

Parameter: max-global-threads Maximum total number of threads. If `max-global-threads=0`, then the ESDM scheduler estimates an optimal value.

Type integer
 Default 0
 Required no

Parameter: accessibility Data access permission rights.

Type string
 Default global
 Required no

Method	Description
--------	-------------

global	data is accessible from all nodes, e.g., shared file system
local	data is accessible from local node only

Parameter: max-fragment-size The amount of data that may be written into a single fragment. The amount is given in bytes.

Type integer
 Default 10485760
 Required no

Parameter: fragmentation-method A string identifying the algorithm to use to split a chunk of data into fragments.

Type string
 Default contiguous
 Required no

Legal values are:

Method	Description
contiguous	This algorithm tries to form fragments that are scattered across memory as little as possible. As such, it is expected to yield the best possible write performance. However, if a transposition is performed when reading the data back, performance may be poor. Splitting a dataspace of size (50, 80, 100) into fragments of 2000 entries results in fragments of size (1, 20, 100).
equalized	This algorithm tries to form fragments that have a similar size in all dimensions. As such, it is expected to perform equally well with all kinds of read requests, but it tends to write scattered data to disk which has to be sequentialized first, imposing a performance penalty on the write side. Splitting a dataspace of size (50, 80, 100) into fragments of at most 2000 entries results in fragments of sizes between (10, 11, 11) and (10, 12, 12).

Table 4: Fragmentation methods

2.3.4 Metadata Parameters

Parameter	Type	Default	Required	Description
id	string	(not set)	(not used)	Unique alpha-numeric identifier.
type	string	(not set)	yes	Metadata type. Reserved for future use.
target	string	(not set)	yes	Path to metadata folder

Table 5: Metadata parameters overview

Parameter: /esdm/metadata/id Unique alpha-numeric identifier.

Type string
 Default (not set)
 Required yes

Parameter: /esdm/metadata/type Metadata type. Reserved for future use.

Type string
 Default (not set)
 Required yes (not used)

Parameter: /esdm/metadata/target Path to the metadata folder.

Type string
 Default (not set)
 Required yes

2.4 Usage

This section illustrates how ESDM can be used with different programming languages and tools. The applications with NetCDF support don't need to be changed or recompiled as long as they are linked against the shared netcdf library. They can simply use the ESDM-NetCDF version and benefit of ESDM. To force them to use the ESDM-NetCDF version, the library can be pre-loaded by `LD_PRELOAD` environment variable.

2.4.1 NetCDF

NetCDF (Network Common Data Form) [11] is a set of software libraries and machine-independent data formats that support the creation, access, and sharing of array-oriented scientific data. In particular, NetCDF is widely used in climate research.

The following examples write and read data to/from a NetCDF file. (For simplicity, we omitted the error handling.)

The write example (`./write`) creates a two dimensional variable in the `esdm://data.nc` file.

```
#include <netcdf.h>

#define NDIMS 2
#define NX 6
#define NY 12

int main() {
    int ncid, x_dimid, y_dimid, varid;
    int dimids[NDIMS];
    int data_out[NX][NY];
    int x, y, retval;

    for (x = 0; x < NX; x++)
        for (y = 0; y < NY; y++)
            data_out[x][y] = x * NY + y;

    nc_create("esdm://data.nc", NC_CLOBBER, &ncid);
    nc_def_dim(ncid, "x", NX, &x_dimid);
    nc_def_dim(ncid, "y", NY, &y_dimid);

    dimids[0] = x_dimid;
    dimids[1] = y_dimid;

    nc_def_var(ncid, "var1", NC_INT, NDIMS, dimids, &varid);
    nc_enddef(ncid);
    nc_put_var_int(ncid, varid, &data_out[0][0]);
    nc_close(ncid);
    return 0;
}
```

The read example (`./read`) reads this variable.

```
#include <stdlib.h>
#include <stdio.h>
#include <netcdf.h>

int main() {
    int ncid, varid;
    int data_in[6][12];
    int x, y, retval;

    nc_open("esdm://data.nc", NC_NOWRITE, &ncid);
    nc_inq_varid(ncid, "var1", &varid);
    nc_get_var_int(ncid, varid, &data_in[0][0]);

    // do something with data ...

    nc_close(ncid);
    return 0;
}
```

For a successful run ESDM requires three things. Firstly, the `esdm.conf` file must be located in the search path. In this case, it is the current directory. Secondly, ESDM requires an initialized ESDM directory structure. If not existing, it can be created by the `mkfs.esdm` tool. Thirdly, files need to be prefixed with `esdm://`. This prefix is an indicator to the NetCDF library to redirect data to ESDM. Otherwise, NetCDF will work as usual and create an `*.nc` file.

The following script initialize the ESDM directory structure and runs the two examples.

```
#!/bin/bash
mkfs.esdm -g -l --create --remove --ignore-errors
./write
./read
```

Currently, ESDM does not provide a full compatibility to NetCDF. The NetCDF compatibility is documented in the report released in https://github.com/ESiWACE/esdm-netcdf/blob/master/libsrcesdm_test/report/report.pdf.

2.4.2 CDO

The Climate Data Operator (CDO) software is a collection of many operators for standard processing of climate and forecast model data. The operators include simple statistical and arithmetic functions, data selection and subsampling tools, and spatial interpolation. CDO was developed to have the same set of processing functions for GRIB and NetCDF datasets in one package. The Climate Data Interface is used for the fast and file format independent access to GRIB and NetCDF datasets. To enable ESDM, the files need the `esdm://` prefix. In the example data is converted from GRIB to NetCDF format and written by ESDM according to the configuration in the `esdm.conf` file.

```
#!/bin/bash
mkfs.esdm -g -l --create --remove --ignore-errors
cdo -f nc -copy data.nc esdm://data.nc
```

2.4.3 XIOS

XIOS [15], standing for XML-IO-Server, is a library dedicated to I/O management, primarily designed to manage NetCDF outputs of climate models. Its main features are management of output diagnostics and history files, temporal post-processing operations, (e.g., average, min, max) and spatial post-processing operations (e.g., arithmetic operations, re-gridding). XIOS simplifies I/O management, by reducing the number of I/O operations and arguments in the source code. The output definitions are outsourced into XML files, which can be changed without re-compilation of the source code. XIOS achieves high performance by asynchronous and parallel I/O.

1. Prerequisites
 - Install ESDM
 - Install ESDM-NetCDF
 - Install NetCDF-Fortran interface

2. Checkout XIOS code

```
svn checkout http://forge.ipsl.jussieu.fr/ioserver/svn/XIOS/trunk
```

3. Add to `bld.cfg`

```
bld::tool::cflags the ESDM include directory of the installation
bld::tool::ldflags the ESDM lib directory and add it also as rpath -Wl,--rpath=<ESDM lib directory>
```

4. Modify `arch.env`. Change the NetCDF directory to the ESDM dir
5. On some Linux distribution `gmake` may be not available. Fortunately, `make` provides the necessary functionality.

```
sudo ln -s /usr/bin/make /usr/bin/gmake
./make_xios --dev --arch GCC_LINUX
```

6. Check that the proper NetCDF library was linked. This should output the NetCDF library created from ESDM.

```
ldd bin/test_client.exe |grep netcdf
```

7. Fix `iodef.xml` file:

```
cp inputs/iodef.xml .
Change <file id="output" name="esdm://output" enabled=".TRUE.">
```

8. Create ESDM configuration file in the local directory

```
cp <ESDM install directory>/src/test/esdm.conf .
```

9. Create ESDM data directories

```
export PATH=<ESDM install directory>/bin/:$PATH
mkfs.esdm -g -l --create --remove --ignore-errors
```

10. Run XIOS MPMD with OpenMPI:

```
mpiexec -np 2 bin/xios_server.exe : -np 3 bin/test_client.exe
```

2.4.4 Python

The patched NetCDF4-Python module is able to redirect I/O to ESDM if the file name contains the `esdm://` prefix, `esdm.conf` is located in the search path, and the ESDM directory structure is initialized with the `mkfs.esdm` tool. The following example illustrates write access to a NetCDF file.

```
#!/usr/bin/env python3

from netCDF4 import Dataset
import numpy as np

root_grp = Dataset('esdm://ncfile.nc', 'w', format='NETCDF4')
#root_grp = Dataset('py_netcdf4.nc', 'w')
root_grp.description = 'Example simulation data'

ndim = 128 # Size of the matrix ndim*ndim
xdimension = 0.75
ydimension = 0.75

# dimensions
root_grp.createDimension('time', None)
root_grp.createDimension('x', ndim)
root_grp.createDimension('y', ndim)

#variables
time = root_grp.createVariable('time', 'f8', ('time',))
x = root_grp.createVariable('x', 'f4', ('x',))
y = root_grp.createVariable('y', 'f4', ('y',))
field = root_grp.createVariable('field', 'f8', ('time', 'x', 'y',))

#data
x_range = np.linspace(0, xdimension, ndim)
y_range = np.linspace(0, ydimension, ndim)
x[:] = x_range
y[:] = y_range
for i in range(5):
    time[i] = i*50.0
    field[i,:,:] = np.random.uniform(size=(len(x_range), len(y_range)))

root_grp.close()
```

2.4.5 Dask

Dask is able to utilize ESDM by redirection I/O to the patched NetCDF4-Python module. By passing the `engine=netcdf4` argument to the `to_netcdf()` function we can make sure, that the correct engine is used in the background. We have to take care, that `esdm.conf` is located in the search path and that the ESDM directory structure is initialized by the `mkfs.esdm` tool.

```
#!/usr/bin/env python
import xarray as xr
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
ds = xr.Dataset(
    {"vari": [1,2,3,4,5,6]},
)
ds.to_netcdf(path="esdm://ncfile.nc", format='NETCDF4', engine="netcdf4")
```

```
#!/usr/bin/env python3
import xarray as xr
ds = xr.open_dataset('esdm://ncfile.nc', engine='netcdf4')
print(ds)
```

2.4.6 NetCDF-Bench

NetCDF Performance Benchmark Tool (NetCDF-Bench) was developed to measure NetCDF I/O performance on devices ranging from notebooks to large HPC systems. It mimics the typical I/O behaviour of scientific climate applications and captures the performance on each node/process. In the end, it aggregates the data to the human-readable summary.

Initialize ESDM directory structure by means of `mkfs.esdm` and make sure `esdm.conf` is located in the search path. The benchmark can be run by the following script.

```
#!/bin/bash
mkfs.esdm -g -l --create --remove --ignore-errors
benchtool -r -w -f=esdm://data.nc
```

2.4.7 Paraview

ParaView is an open-source, multi-platform data analysis and visualization application. It can load a variety of different data formats, visualize the data and analyse it by qualitative and quantitative techniques. In particular, Paraview supports the NetCDF data format and different grid types, and is often used in climate and earth science. The data import capabilities in Paraview are implemented as plugins. The NetCDF Plugin is able to load NetCDF files with CF conventions and the CDI Reader Plugin is able to load ICON data [1]. We could successfully test both them.

The ESDM-NetCDF library need to be linked to Paraview. On Linux this can be done by `LD_PRELOAD` feature, like shown in the following script. The `$INSTPATH` variable show to the ESDM-NetCDF library location.

```
LD_PRELOAD=$INSTPATH/libnetcdf.so paraview
```

A NetCDF file was converted to ESDM representation and loaded in Paraview via the NetCDF plugin. Loading data works slightly different compared to ordinary NetCDF files. If the pseudo ESDM file (an empty file with the `:esdm` suffix) exists, then it can be selected in the open dialog as usual. Otherwise, the user has to know the file name and must enter it manually. Another difference is that on the left side in the GUI (see Figure 3) the data set is labeled by the `:esdm` suffix. Once data is loaded, other steps can be done as usual.

3 ESDM Developer Guide

This section aims to give a quick conceptual overview of the API that is available to programs which link directly to ESDM. It is not meant to be exhaustive, but rather to give enough background information so

Figure 3: Visualization of ice data set in Paraview. Data source is an ESDM file.

that reading the documentation of the ESDM API becomes easy. The intended audience of this guide are developers of scientific applications who wish to benefit of the full potential of the ESDM API.

Readers who are interested in using an ESDM file system with a NetCDF based application should read the users guide instead. Unfortunately, there is no guide for ESDM backend developers and ESDM core contributors yet.

3.1 Internal Data Model

The first thing to understand is the data model used by ESDM. This data model is very similar to that employed by NetCDF, but it adds some abstractions. This section describes the model.

3.1.1 Dataspace

A data space describes the layout of data in memory. It is a mapping of logical data space to sequential bytes in memory. All data handled by ESDM is associated with a data space. Mostly the data spaces are user-provided. Several copies of the same data may use distinct dataspace. In this case, ESDM allows users to transform data from one layout to another by providing a source and a destination data space (`esdm_dataspace_copy_data()`). User code needs to provide a data space when it defines a variable (here, the data layout part is irrelevant), when it stores data, and when it reads data.

The logical data space is always a multidimensional, axis-aligned box in ESDM. As such, a data space consists of the following information:

- the dimension count
- start and end coordinates for each axis
- a data type describing a single value within the multidimensional array
- (data serialization information)

The data serialization information is usually implicit. By default, ESDM assumes a C multidimensional array layout. Fortran programs will need to set explicitly the data serialization information to match Fortran's inverse dimension order. The data serialization information (`stride`) can also achieve unorthodox effects like arrays with holes or replicating a single 2D slice along a third axis.

Creating and destroying dataspace ESDM provides two distinct mechanisms to create a data space: A generic API that allocates the data space on the heap and an API to create a throw-away data space on the stack quickly.

The generic API The functions used to create dataspace are:

- `esdm_dataspace_create()` Construct a data space with a given dimension count, size, and datatype. It assumes that the hypercube starts at (0, 0, ..., 0) and C data layout.
- `esdm_dataspace_create_full()` Like `esdm_dataspace_create()`, but allows the user to specify start coordinates.
- `esdm_dataspace_copy()` Copy constructor.
- `esdm_dataspace_subspace()` Create a data space that contains a subset of the logical data space of its parent data space. It copies the datatype and assumes the C data layout for the subspace. If this is not desirable, follow up with a call to `esdm_dataspace_copyDataLayout()`.
- `esdm_dataspace_makeContiguous()` Create a data space with the same logical space and datatype, but which uses the C data layout.

All these functions return a pointer to a new data space **which must be destroyed with a call to `esdm_dataspace_destroy()`**.

Data layout can only be set explicitly after a data space has been created. This is done by a call to `esdm_dataspace_set_stride()` or to `esdm_dataspace_copyDataLayout()`. The first allows the user to specify any standard data layout, including but not limited to Fortran's data layout. The latter assumes that the data space will access the same data buffer as the data space from which the data layout is copied. As such, `esdm_dataspace_copyDataLayout()` is very convenient for data subsetting operations.

The simple API For convenience and performance reasons, ESDM provides preprocessor macros that allocate a data space on the stack. Macros are provided for 1D, 2D, and 3D data spaces and come in variants that either assume start coordinates at the origin of the coordinate system, or allow the offset to be specified explicitly. The macros without explicit start coordinates are:

```
esdm_dataspace_1d()
esdm_dataspace_2d()
esdm_dataspace_3d()
```

The macros that take start coordinates simply add an "o" to the end of the name:

```
esdm_dataspace_1do()
esdm_dataspace_2do()
esdm_dataspace_3do()
```

The result of these macros is a value of type `esdm_simple_dspace_t`, which is a struct containing a single member `ptr` which includes the pointer value that can subsequently be used in all ESDM calls that require a data space, i.e., a typical usage might be:

```
esdm_simple_dspace_t region = esdm_dataspace_2do(x, width, y, height, type);
esdm_read(dataset, buffer, region.ptr);
```

As the `esdm_simple_dspace_t` lives on the stack, **it must not be destroyed with `esdm_dataspace_destroy()`**. It ceases to exist when the surrounding block exits.

3.1.2 Dataset

A dataset in ESDM is what a variable is in NetCDF or HDF5. Each data set is associated with a data space that describes the logical extends of the data, and it acts as a container for data written into this logical space.

There is no requirement to fill the entire logical space with data. Usually, reading nonexistent data results in an error. However, a dataset can also be associated with a fill value to handle data with holes seamlessly.

There is also no requirement to write non-overlapping data. When write accesses overlap, ESDM will assume that both accesses place the same data in the overlapping area. If this condition does not hold, there is no guarantee which data will be returned on a read.

In addition to the data and the logical space, datasets can also contain several attributes. Like attributes in NetCDF, these are meant to associate metadata with a dataset.

User code can either create a dataset with `esdm_dataset_create()` or look up an existing dataset from a container with `esdm_dataset_open()`. In either case, the reference to the dataset must later be dropped by a call to `esdm_dataset_close()`. A dataset can also be deleted with a call to `esdm_dataset_delete()` which will remove its data from the file system, as well as its name and link from its container.

3.1.3 Container

Containers provide a means to organize and retrieve datasets. When a dataset is created, it is added to a container and associated with a name for later retrieval.

Like datasets, containers are created with `esdm_container_create()` or looked up from the file system with `esdm_container_open()` and need to be closed with `esdm_container_close()` when their reference is not required anymore. Closing a container requires closing all datasets it contains first. `esdm_container_delete()` removes a container from the file system.

3.1.4 Grid

The grid abstraction exists for performance reasons only: While it is possible to think of a data set as a set of possibly overlapping chunks of data, it is surprisingly hard to determine minimal sets of chunks to satisfy a read request. On the other hand, user code generally does not use overlapping chunks of data. Instead, user code can be assumed to work on (semi-)regular non-overlapping chunks of data. Passing this chunking information to ESDM allows the library to make the right decisions faster.

Grids also allow user code to inquire how the data is available on disk, allowing consumer code to iterate over complete and non-overlapping sets of data chunks in the most efficient fashion. To work with grids, the header `esdm-grid.h` must be included.

Like a data space, a grid covers an axis-aligned hyper box in the logical space. This space is called the grid's domain, and it is defined when a grid is created with `esdm_grid_create()`, `esdm_grid_createSimple()` allows omitting the start coordinates to use the origin as one corner of the hyper box.

Once a grid has been created, its axes can be subdivided individually by calls to `esdm_grid_subdivide()`. It allows the user to specify all the bounds for an axis explicitly. In many contexts, however, it will be simpler to use `esdm_grid_subdivideFixed()` or `esdm_grid_subdivideFlexible()` which instruct ESDM to generate bounds in a regular way. The fixed subdivision will produce intervals of a given size. Flexible subdivision instructs ESDM to generate a specific number of similar size intervals.

After the grid axis has been defined, individual grid cells may be turned into subgrids via `esdm_grid_createSubgrid()`. After this, the parent grid axes are fixed, and the subdivision calls cannot be used anymore. On the other hand, the subgrid is a newly created grid with the parent grid's cell bounds as its domain. Usually, user code will follow up with calls to `esdm_grid_subdivide*()` on the subgrid to define its axes. Subgrids may be constructed recursively to any depth.

This subgrid feature is useful to define grids with semi-regular decompositions: For instance, an image may be decomposed into stripes, which are themselves decomposed into rectangles, but the rectangle bounds of one

stripe do not match those of another stripe. Such semi-regular decompositions are a typical result of load balancing of earth system simulations.

Once a grids structure has been defined fully, it can be used to read/write data via `esdm_read_grid()` and `esdm_write_grid()`. Parallel applications will want to distribute the grid to all involved processes first by calling `esdm_mpi_grid_bcast()` (include `esdm-mpi.h` for this). Both use a grid for input/output, and communicating it over MPI will fix the grid's structure, prohibiting future calls to subdivide axes or create subgrids.

It is possible to iterate over all (sub-)cells of a grid. This is done using an iterator, the three relevant functions are `esdm_gridIterator_create()`, `esdm_gridIterator_next()` and `esdm_gridIterator_destroy()`. This is meant to be used by readers who inquire about an available grid from a dataset using `esdm_dataset_grids()`. This method of reading avoids any cropping or stitching together of data chunks within ESDM, delivering the best possible performance.

Grids always remain in possession of their data space. Consequently, it is not necessary to dispose of them explicitly. However, closing a data space invalidates all associated (sub-)grids.

3.2 Usage examples

Learning the usage of an API is easiest by seeing it in action in concrete examples. As such, this section provides four relatively basic examples of how the ESDM API is supposed to be used, which nevertheless cover all the necessary core functionality.

3.2.1 Basic writing

The simplest way to write a greyscale image to ESDM is as follows:

```
//assume image data stored in either
uint16_t imageBuffer[height][width];
uint16_t (*imageBuffer)[width] = malloc(height*sizeof*imageBuffer);

//initialize ESDM
esdm_status result = esdm_init();
assert(result == ESDM_SUCCESS);

//create the container, dataspace, and dataset
esdm_container_t* container;
//pass true to allow overwriting of an existing container
result = esdm_container_create("path/to/container", false, &container);
assert(result == ESDM_SUCCESS);
//the data is 2D and consists of uint64_t values
esdm_simple_dspace_t space =
    esdm_dataspace_2d(height, width, SMD_TYPE_UINT16); esdm_dataset_t* dataset;
result = esdm_dataset_create(container, "myImage", space.ptr, &dataset);
assert(result == ESDM_SUCCESS);

//write the data
result = esdm_write(dataset, imageBuffer, space.ptr);
assert(result == ESDM_SUCCESS);

//cleanup
result = esdm_dataset_close(dataset);
assert(result == ESDM_SUCCESS);
result = esdm_container_close(container);
assert(result == ESDM_SUCCESS);

//bring down ESDM
result = esdm_finalize();
assert(result == ESDM_SUCCESS);
```

In this example, the same dataspace is used to create the dataset and write the data, writing all the data in one large piece. Although it is not necessary, the data spaces that are passed to `esdm_write()` may be

smaller than the data set, calling `esdm_write()` as many times as required to write the entire data.

3.2.2 Grid-based writing

When using grid-based writing, creating of the container and the dataset is the same. The creation of the grid, however, is added explicitly. In this case, we are going to slice a 3D data space into ten slices of similar size along the z-axis and into rows of 256 lines along the y axis:

```
// define the grid
esdm_grid_t* grid;
result = esdm_grid_createSimple(dataset, 3, (int64_t[3]){depth, height, width}, &grid);
assert(result == ESDM_SUCCESS);
// the last parameter allows the last interval to be smaller than 256 lines
result = esdm_grid_subdivideFixed(grid, 1, 256, true);
assert(result == ESDM_SUCCESS);
result = esdm_grid_subdivideFlexible(grid, 0, 10);
assert(result == ESDM_SUCCESS);

for(int64_t z0 = 0, slice = 0, curDepth; z0 < depth; z0 += curDepth, slice++) {
    // inquire the depth of the current slice
    // use of esdm_grid_subdivideFlexible() generally
    // requires use of a grid bounds inquiry function
    int64_t z1;
    result = esdm_grid_getBound(grid, 0, slice + 1, &z1);
    assert(result == ESDM_SUCCESS);
    curDepth = z1 - z0;

    for(int64_t row = 0; row*256 < height; row++) {
        // compute the height of the current row
        // we can calculate this ourselves as we have used esdm_grid_subdivideFixed()
        int64_t height = (row < height/256 ? 256 : height - row*256);

        // set contents of dataBuffer

        // use the grid to write one chunk of data, the grid knows
        // to which dataset it belongs
        result = esdm_write_grid(
            grid,
            esdm_dataspace_3do(z0, curDepth, row*256, height, 0, width, SMD_TYPE_DOUBLE).ptr,
            dataBuffer);
        assert(result == ESDM_SUCCESS);
    }
}

// no need to cleanup the grid, it belongs to the dataset and
// will be disposed off when the dataset is closed
```

3.2.3 Simple reading

Reading data is very similar to writing it. Nevertheless, a simple example is given to read an entire dataset in one piece:

```
// open the container and dataset, and inquire the dataspace
esdm_container_t* container;
result = esdm_container_open("path/to/container", ESDM_MODE_FLAG_READ, &container);
assert(result == ESDM_SUCCESS);
esdm_dataset_t* dataset;
result = esdm_dataset_open(container, "myDataset", ESDM_MODE_FLAG_READ, &dataset);
assert(result == ESDM_SUCCESS);
esdm_dataspace_t* dataspace;
// this returns a reference to the internal dataspace, do not destroy or modify it
esdm_dataset_get_dataspace(dataset, &dataspace);

// allocate a buffer large enough to hold the data and generate a dataspace for it
// the buffer will be in contiguous C data layout
result = esdm_dataspace_makeContiguous(dataspace, &dataspace);
assert(result == ESDM_SUCCESS);
int64_t bufferSize = esdm_dataspace_total_bytes(dataspace);
void* buffer = malloc(bufferSize);
```

```

// read the data
result = esdm_read(dataset, buffer, dataspace);
assert(result == ESDM_SUCCESS);

// do stuff with buffer and dataspace

// cleanup
// esdm_dataspace_makeContiguous() creates a new dataspace
result = esdm_dataspace_destroy(dataspace);
assert(result == ESDM_SUCCESS);
result = esdm_dataset_close(dataset);
assert(result == ESDM_SUCCESS);
result = esdm_container_close(container);
assert(result == ESDM_SUCCESS);

```

3.2.4 Grid-based reading

Reading an entire dataset as a single chunk is generally a terrible idea. Data sets, especially those generated by earth system models, can be massive, many times larger than the available main memory. Reading a dataset in the form of reader-defined chunks is possible with `esdm_read()`, but not necessarily efficient. The chunks on disk may not match those which are used to read, requiring `esdm_read()` to

- read multiple chunks from disk and stitch them together,
- and to read more data from disk than is required.

If the dataset has been written using a grid, this grid can be recovered to inform the reading process of the actual data layout on disk:

```

// open the container and dataset, and inquire the available grids
esdm_container_t* container;
result = esdm_container_open("path/to/container", ESDM_MODE_FLAG_READ, &container);
assert(result == ESDM_SUCCESS);
esdm_dataset_t* dataset;
result = esdm_dataset_open(container, "myDataset", ESDM_MODE_FLAG_READ, &dataset);
assert(result == ESDM_SUCCESS);
int64_t gridCount;
esdm_grid_t** grids;
result = esdm_dataset_grids(dataset, &gridCount, &grids);
assert(result == ESDM_SUCCESS);

// select a grid, here we just use the first one
assert(gridCount >= 1);
esdm_grid_t* grid = grids[0];
free(grids); //we are responsible to free this array

// iterate over the data, reading the data one stored chunk at a time
esdm_gridIterator_t* iterator;
result = esdm_gridIterator_create(grid, &iterator);
assert(result == ESDM_SUCCESS);
while(true) {
    esdm_dataspace_t* cellSpace;
    result = esdm_gridIterator_next(&iterator, 1, &cellSpace);
    assert(result == ESDM_SUCCESS);

    if(!iterator) break;

    // allocate a buffer large enough to hold the data
    int64_t bufferSize = esdm_dataspace_total_bytes(cellSpace);
    void* buffer = malloc(bufferSize);

    // read the data
    result = esdm_read_grid(grid, cellSpace, buffer);
    assert(result == ESDM_SUCCESS);

    // do stuff with buffer and cellSpace

    // cleanup

```

```

    free(buffer);
    result = esdm_dataspace_destroy(cellSpace);
    assert(result == ESDM_SUCCESS);
}

// cleanup
// no cleanup necessary for the iterator, it has already been destroyed
// by esdm_gridIterator_next()
result = esdm_dataset_close(dataset);
assert(result == ESDM_SUCCESS);
result = esdm_container_close(container);
assert(result == ESDM_SUCCESS);

```

4 ESDM Performance Measurement

With performance tests, we can estimate the actual speed-up through the use of ESDM. The test are chosen so that they mimic I/O-intensive climate simulations and support NetCDF. This makes it relatively easy to integrate the ESDM-NetCDF library by linking it with [LD_PRELOAD](#).

4.1 NetCDF-Bench

By using NetCDF-bench⁷, we measured the NetCDF performance at the Mistral⁸ supercomputer for several library choices with ESDM and HDF5. We extended the benchmark to offset the read access by one rank to prevent the read-cache usage, and implemented a file-per-process option that will serve as an optimistic performance baseline as some models use such a configuration.

The configuration used NetCDF 4.6.2 and HDF5 1.10.7⁹. The NetCDF-benchmark used the data dimension 10:12000:12000:200 (time:x:y:z) with floating point data. Thus, a total file size of 1.1 TiB was read or written from the Lustre01 file system.

At runtime, for NetCDF file-per-process (nc-fpp) and the ESDM configurations, a Lustre stripe count of 1 was chosen, while for the shared file configuration (nc), all 124 stripes (OSTs) have been used. The esdm-lustre-both configuration used ESDM to place data on both Lustre file system.

The results obtained for 100 nodes are shown in Figure 4. It can be observed that nc-fpp achieves significantly better performance than the shared file configuration. ESDM yields best performance and significantly better read performance. Using both file systems with ESDM increased performance slightly. We believe there is further room for optimization here, as indicated by the ESDM benchmarks.

We were surprised to see that the NetCDF write performance is only 1/5th of the previously measured ESDM benchmarks. As the DKRZ file system is at the end of life, it might be the ageing file system itself and performed software updates that impact the observable performance negatively. Nevertheless, the performance comparison between NetCDF and NetCDF with ESDM are conducted on the same system and, hence, fair.

4.2 Shallow-Water-Equations

The C++ code for shallow-water-equations (SWE) from TU Munich¹⁰ supports NetCDF. As this code is very compact, it allowed for showcasing modifications of APIs and conversions to the ESDM API and particularly the ESDM write-streaming API. The RadialDamBreakScenario (simulates 15s) is used.

This code is configured to run with ten timesteps and a dimensionality of $(x,y) = (23040,23040)$. The different

⁷<https://github.com/joobog/netcdf-bench>

⁸<https://www.dkrz.de/up/systems/mistral>

⁹We used the default configurations without specific tuning settings as this is the typical use case.

¹⁰<https://github.com/TUM-I5/SWE>

Figure 4: NetCDF performance on 100 Nodes at Mistral

variables are set up in Listing 6¹¹. It performs during the simulation 10 I/O steps that follow the behavior in Listing 7.

The data access of the 2D fields is of key interests. As it turns out, each column is written independently; the code is shown in Listing 8.

```
//create a netCDF-file, an existing file will be replaced
status = nc_create(fileName.c_str(), NC_NETCDF4, &dataFile);

//dimensions
int l_timeDim, l_xDim, l_yDim;
nc_def_dim(dataFile, "time", NC_UNLIMITED, &l_timeDim);
nc_def_dim(dataFile, "x", nX, &l_xDim);
nc_def_dim(dataFile, "y", nY, &l_yDim);

//variables (TODO: add rest of CF-1.5)
int l_xVar, l_yVar;

nc_def_var(dataFile, "time", NC_FLOAT, 1, &l_timeDim, &timeVar);
nc_put_att_text(timeVar, "long_name", "Time");
// the word "since" is important for the paraview reader
nc_put_att_text(timeVar, "units", "seconds since simulation start");

nc_def_var(dataFile, "x", NC_FLOAT, 1, &l_xDim, &l_xVar);
nc_def_var(dataFile, "y", NC_FLOAT, 1, &l_yDim, &l_yVar);

// variables, fastest changing index is on the right (C syntax),
// will be mirrored by the librarybasicstyle=\scriptsize,
int dims[] = {l_timeDim, l_yDim, l_xDim};
nc_def_var(dataFile, "h", NC_FLOAT, 3, dims, &hVar);
nc_def_var(dataFile, "hu", NC_FLOAT, 3, dims, &huVar);
nc_def_var(dataFile, "hv", NC_FLOAT, 3, dims, &hvVar);
nc_def_var(dataFile, "b", NC_FLOAT, 2, &dims[1], &bVar);
```

Listing 6: SWE Declaration of NetCDF variables

```
if (timeStep == 0)
// Write bathymetry
writeVarTimeIndependent(b, bVar);
```

¹¹The TODO note stems from the original source code and indicates that the programmer only included the most relevant metadata for NetCDF/CF.

```

//write i_time
nc_put_var1_float(dataFile, timeVar, &timeStep, &i_time);

//the remaining fields are 2D variables
//write water height
writeVarTimeDependent(i_h, hVar);

//write momentum in x-direction
writeVarTimeDependent(i_hu, huVar);

//write momentum in y-direction
writeVarTimeDependent(i_hv, hvVar);

```

Listing 7: SWE Write Iteration

```

void io::NetCdfWriter::writeVarTimeDependent( const Float2D &i_matrix,
                                             int i_ncVariable ) {
    //write col wise, necessary to get rid of the boundary
    //storage in Float2D is col wise
    //read carefully, the dimensions are confusing
    size_t start[] = {timeStep, 0, 0};
    size_t count[] = {1, nY, 1};
    for(unsigned int col = 0; col < nX; col++) {
        start[2] = col; //select col (dim "x")
        nc_put_vara_float(dataFile, i_ncVariable, start, count,
                        &i_matrix[col+boundarySize[0]][boundarySize[2]]); //write col
    }
}

```

Listing 8: SWE Write Time Dependent

For using ESDM, the code to declare variables is illustrated in Listing 9 and the changed `writeVarTimeDependent()` function in Listing 10. We did not yet provide too much syntactic sugar for the declaration of variables, but the write stream API is optimized. Note that the created ESDM container contains all the metadata such that it can be later opened with the `esdm://`-prefix or `:esdm`-suffix as if it would be a NetCDF file.

```

esdm_status ret = esdm_mpi_container_create(MPL_COMM_WORLD, "swe", true, &container);
checkRet(ret);

if(rank == 0){
    smd_attr_t * attr;
    //set attributes to match CF-1.5 convention
    attr = smd_attr_new("Conventions", SMD_DTYPE_STRING, "CF-1.5");
    esdm_container_link_attribute(container, 1, attr);
    attr = smd_attr_new("title", SMD_DTYPE_STRING, "Computed tsunami solution");
    esdm_container_link_attribute(container, 1, attr);
    attr = smd_attr_new("history", SMD_DTYPE_STRING, "SWE");
    esdm_container_link_attribute(container, 1, attr);
    attr = smd_attr_new("institution", SMD_DTYPE_STRING,
        "Technische Universitaet Muenchen, Department of Informatics, Chair of Scientific Computing");
    esdm_container_link_attribute(container, 1, attr);
    attr = smd_attr_new("source", SMD_DTYPE_STRING, "Bathymetry and displacement data.");
    esdm_container_link_attribute(container, 1, attr);
    attr = smd_attr_new("references", SMD_DTYPE_STRING, "http://www5.in.tum.de/SWE");
    esdm_container_link_attribute(container, 1, attr);
    attr = smd_attr_new("comment", SMD_DTYPE_STRING,
        "SWE is free software and licensed under the GNU General Public License."
        "Remark: In general this does not hold for the used input data.");
    esdm_container_link_attribute(container, 1, attr);
}

//variables add rest of CF-1.5
esdm_dataspace_t *dspace;
int64_t b1[] = {0};
ret = esdm_dataspace_create(1, b1, SMD_DTYPE_FLOAT, &dspace);
checkRet(ret);
ret = esdm_mpi_dataset_create(MPL_COMM_WORLD, container, "time", dspace, &tvar);
{
    char * const names[] = { (char*)"time" };
}

```

```

    esdm_dataset_name_dims(tvar, names);
}
checkRet(ret);

if(rank == 0){
    smd_attr_t * attr;
    attr = smd_attr_new("long_name", SMD_DTYPE_STRING, "Time");
    esdm_dataset_link_attribute(tvar, 1, attr);
    attr = smd_attr_new("units", SMD_DTYPE_STRING, "seconds since simulation start");
    esdm_dataset_link_attribute(tvar, 1, attr);
}

esdm_dataset_t * xvar;
esdm_dataset_t * yvar;
{
    int64_t b[] = {(int64_t) fullX};
    ret = esdm_dataspace_create(1, b, SMD_DTYPE_FLOAT, & dspace);
    checkRet(ret);
    ret = esdm_mpi_dataset_create(MPI_COMM_WORLD, container, "x", dspace, & xvar);
    checkRet(ret);
    char * const names[] = { (char*) "x" };
    esdm_dataset_name_dims(xvar, names);
}
{
    int64_t b[] = {(int64_t) fullY};
    ret = esdm_dataspace_create(1, b, SMD_DTYPE_FLOAT, & dspace);
    checkRet(ret);
    ret = esdm_mpi_dataset_create(MPI_COMM_WORLD, container, "y", dspace, & yvar);
    checkRet(ret);
    char * const names[] = { (char*) "y" };
    esdm_dataset_name_dims(yvar, names);
}
{
    char * const names[] = { (char*) "time", (char*) "y", (char*) "x" };
    int64_t b[] = {0, (int64_t) fullY, (int64_t) fullX};
    ret = esdm_dataspace_create(3, b, SMD_DTYPE_FLOAT, & dspace);
    ret = esdm_mpi_dataset_create(MPI_COMM_WORLD, container, "h", dspace, & hvar);
    checkRet(ret);
    ret = esdm_dataspace_create(3, b, SMD_DTYPE_FLOAT, & dspace);
    ret = esdm_mpi_dataset_create(MPI_COMM_WORLD, container, "hu", dspace, & huvar);
    checkRet(ret);
    ret = esdm_dataspace_create(3, b, SMD_DTYPE_FLOAT, & dspace);
    ret = esdm_mpi_dataset_create(MPI_COMM_WORLD, container, "hv", dspace, & hvvar);
    checkRet(ret);

    esdm_dataset_name_dims(hvar, names);
    esdm_dataset_name_dims(huvar, names);
    esdm_dataset_name_dims(hvvar, names);
}
{
    int64_t b[] = {(int64_t) fullY, (int64_t) fullX};
    char * const names[] = { (char*) "y", (char*) "x" };
    ret = esdm_dataspace_create(2, b, SMD_DTYPE_FLOAT, & dspace);
    ret = esdm_mpi_dataset_create(MPI_COMM_WORLD, container, "b", dspace, & bvar);
    checkRet(ret);
    esdm_dataset_name_dims(bvar, names);
}
}

```

Listing 9: SWE Declaration of ESDM variables

```

void io::ESDMWriter::writeVarTimeDependent( const Float2D &i_matrix, esdm_dataset_t * dset) {
    //write col wise, necessary to get rid of the boundary
    //storage in Float2D is organized column-wise
    int64_t offset[] = {(int64_t) timeStep, offsetY, offsetX};
    int64_t size[] = {1, (int64_t) nY, (int64_t) nX};
    esdm_status ret;
    esdm_wstream_float_t ew;
    esdm_wstream_start(& ew, dset, 3, offset, size);

    for(int y = 0; y < nY; y++){
        for(int x = 0; x < nX; x++){
            esdm_wstream_pack(ew, i_matrix[x + boundarySize[0]]
                               [boundarySize[2] + y]);
        }
    }
}

```

```

esdm_wstream_commit(ew);
}

```

Listing 10: SWE Write Code with ESDM

The simulation had been executed on 10 nodes. It turned out that to simulate 1 second model time, it takes about 2267 seconds wallclock time, which for 15 seconds model time exceeds the available runtime of 8 hours per job. For ESDM on Lustre01, it had performed 4 I/O phases, each taking around 6 seconds.

With NetCDF and HDF5, after 15 minutes, the initial write out had been aborted, each process having created about an individual 200 MByte file. Note that in this case, the NetCDF/ESDM backend is not helping much either, as each column will be stored into an individual object which overwhelms the storage server.

5 An example ESDM use case: Ophidia

Ophidia is a CMCC¹² research effort targeting High-Performance Data Analytics (HPDA) for eScience. It addresses the challenges related to scientific data management and analysis by joining HPC paradigms with scientific data analytics approaches [5, 2]. The Ophidia framework provides in-memory, parallel, server-side data analysis and I/O and implements an internal storage model, leveraging the datacube abstraction from the Online Analytical Processing (OLAP) field and a hierarchical organization to partition and distribute large multi-dimensional datasets. Ophidia is primarily used in the field of climate and weather, but it has also been successfully employed in other domains thanks to its flexible architecture and storage model.

5.1 Integration of the Ophidia framework with ESDM

Ophidia provides a complete stack for data analytics through a multi-layered architecture. Figure 5 shows an updated diagram (with respect to ESiWACE2 milestone MS5.1 [4]) of the integrated version of the Ophidia framework with the ESDM middleware. The ESDM integration aims to extend the Ophidia framework to transparently support import and export over heterogeneous storage devices using the ESDM middleware features presented in this report.

The upper layer of the architecture consists of the front-end server responsible for managing the client-side incoming requests. The second layer consists of the framework for the execution of parallel operators. The operators can be executed on multiple compute nodes over the whole datacube. More than 50 operators are provided to manage and process both metadata and data. Among these, data import and export operators from and into NetCDF files are also available. Instead, the third layer performs I/O and analytics operations on the data stored on the file system and in the Ophidia storage model. The I/O and analytics servers manage the datacube fragments and run the Ophidia primitives (array-based UDF functions) over this data.

In particular, as can be seen from Figure 5, the second and third layers of the Ophidia architecture are those affected by the extensions for the integration with the ESDM.

The integration has been performed following two different approaches: (i) by linking the framework components against the ESDM-NetCDF library, similarly to what presented for other systems in Section 2.4, and (ii) through the development of new operators directly integrating the ESDM API. To this end, the framework component and I/O and analytics servers have been extended to interact with the ESDM middleware, besides the POSIX file system. The following subsections delve into the implementation details.

5.2 Integration through the ESDM-NetCDF library

A preliminary integration of the ESDM features in the Ophidia framework has been performed through the ESDM-enabled NetCDF library called `esdm-netcdf` (<https://github.com/ESiWACE/esdm-netcdf>), already

¹²The Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate Change

Figure 5: Integration of Ophidia and ESDM components for enhanced I/O

introduced in previous sections. This module extends the well-known NetCDF API [12] acting as a layer towards the ESDM middleware. This approach has been initially taken into consideration to achieve a first integration without having to re-implement the I/O operators for a different interface and to limit changes in the code. The goal was to evaluate the feasibility of the integration and check for possible mismatches and issues in the Ophidia framework while using the underlying ESDM middleware. Hence, it can be considered as a preparatory step for the second integration approach discussed in the following subsection.

More in detail, since the Ophidia import and export operators already exploit the NetCDF API for I/O, the integration of Ophidia and ESDM consisted in a code re-build by linking *esdm-netcdf* library in place of the standard NetCDF library. Moreover, some changes in the code were performed to support the ESDM format as input and output names (i.e., with the format `esdm://name`). Two Ophidia modules are involved in this procedure: the framework, which provides the operators, and the I/O and analytics server, which deals with in-memory datacube management.

The ESDM library has been installed on the *Zeus supercomputer* at CMCC to provide a testbed environment; POSIX has been used as the ESDM backend type (see Section 2.3). During the testing phase, some minor issues in the ESDM library were also identified and fixed by the ESDM developers team. The *esdm-netcdf* library has been compiled by linking a thread-safe version of HDF5 library (version 1.10.5) as required for Ophidia.

Through to this approach, the compilation of the Ophidia framework and Ophidia I/O and analytics servers did not introduce particular issues. Of course, the configuration for code building includes references to the *esdm-netcdf* and thread-safe HDF5 libraries cited above. Note that, in the framework case, these libraries are only linked to *import/export drivers*, which are the framework operators devoted to data reading and writing.

The re-built versions of the Ophidia framework and I/O and analytics server have been installed on the Zeus supercomputer and tested by converting some ESDM containers into Ophidia datacubes and vice versa.

Thanks to this approach, all the Ophidia import and export operators have been easily extended with the ESDM middleware. The full set of features, including parallel import/export and direct in-memory data loading are therefore supported.

5.3 Direct integration through the ESDM library

To provide a more tightly integrated implementation, specific import and export Ophidia operators directly using the ESDM API have been developed. The aim of this implementation was to exploit the ESDM API without the intermediate layer of the NetCDF API and to get the native performance from ESDM.

More specifically, two new Ophidia operators have been developed:

- *OPH_IMPORTESDM* converts and loads an ESDM container into an Ophidia datacube;
- *OPH_EXPORTESDM* converts and stores an Ophidia datacube into an ESDM container.

As it can easily be argued, this second approach required a bigger effort with respect to the previous one as the code of the operators had to be adapted and re-written to integrate a new API for I/O. Hence, besides the features for a proper interaction with the middleware, the current implementation has targeted some of the main import and export features available in Ophidia, such as support for customizable parallel data read and write. Future extensions carried out during the project will include support for additional (optional) features. Moreover, the activities performed in the scope of the project's WP5 on "*Data Post-Processing, Analytics and Visualisation*" will leverage these extensions for the introduction of in-flight analytics in the Ophidia framework, possibly also through active-storage kernels. It is noteworthy that both the operators are implemented as MPI applications and hence support parallel I/O.

To this end, the framework's configure module has been also extended to support a new configure option for specifying the path of the ESDM library: `--with-esdm-path=/path/to/ESDM/lib`.

From an implementation standpoint, the operators exploit a subset of the features of the ESDM C API presented in Section 3, mainly related to:

- functions to manage ESDM containers, some examples include
 - `esdm_container_open()`
 - `esdm_container_create()`
 - `esdm_container_get_attributes()`
 - `esdm_container_link_attributes()`
- functions to create ESDM dataspace, using the generic ESDM dataspace API
 - e.g., `esdm_dataspace_create()`
- functions to manage ESDM datasets, such as
 - `esdm_dataset_open()`
 - `esdm_dataset_create()`
 - `esdm_dataset_get_attributes()`
 - `esdm_dataset_link_attribute()`
 - `esdm_dataset_get_name_dims()`
 - `esdm_dataset_get_dataspace()`
- functions to read/write data
 - `esdm_read()`
 - `esdm_write()`

In particular, the operator *OPH_IMPORTESDM* has inherited most of the input arguments from

OPH_IMPORTNC (the Ophidia operator used for loading data from NetCDF files)¹³, although some are not currently supported and will be introduced in future developments. For instance, a sample ESDM object named `esdm://name` containing the variable `temperature` can be simply imported into Ophidia as follows.

```
oph_importesdm src_path=esdm://name;measure=temperature;nhost=1;nfrag=9;ncores=9;exp_dim=lat|lon;
imp_dim=time;ioserver=ophidiaio_memory;
```

In this example, the argument `measure` allows for selecting the dataset in the `container` to be imported (besides related dimensions and metadata), while the optional argument `ioserver` is set to transfer data to in-memory I/O servers. Additionally, the `nhost` and `nfrag` arguments are used to partition the ESDM container in the resulting Ophidia datacube, respectively on multiple nodes and fragments, while the `ncores` argument is used to parallelize the data loading process. In Ophidia, each datacube is, in fact, physically split into multiple fragments consisting of a set of binary-arrays. The `exp_dim` and `imp_dim` arguments are then used by Ophidia to define the structure of the datacube in-memory. In this particular example, the values related to different time steps (`time` dimension) are contiguously stored into the same binary array, with each array referring to the different pairs of latitude and longitude dimension values (according to the Ophidia storage model [6]). Moreover, support to read metadata from ESDM has been implemented and it can be managed through an optional argument called `import_metadata`.

Similarly, the operator `OPH_EXPORTESDM` has inherited most of the input arguments from `OPH_EXPORTNC` (the Ophidia operator used for storing data into NetCDF files)¹⁴. The operator arguments are all optional with the exception of the datacube identifier. For example, the following command can be used to convert the datacube identified by `https://localhost/1/1` into an ESDM object called by default `esdm://measure`, where `measure` is the name of the dataset to be converted; it is worth to mention that `measure` is the name of the main variable used in the Ophidia environment.

```
oph_exportesdm cube=https://localhost/1/1;ncores=9;
```

The command in the example creates an ESDM object for each fragment that the input datacube is split into; the `ncores` argument is used to parallelize the data storing process. The output ESDM object name can also be customized by using the `output_name` argument, e.g. `output_name=test` will result in `esdm://test_i` objects (with `i` referring to the `i-th` fragment). Also in this case, the export operator supports the writing of metadata into an ESDM object, through the optional argument called `export_metadata`.

6 Ensemble Analysis and Data Reduction using XIOS

The XIOS is an I/O management library for weather and climate. It can be used directly with NetCDF or with the ESDM. For ESDM integration into XIOS it is sufficient to link the ESDM-NetCDF libraries as shown in the usage example in the user's guide.

The following two demonstrators use XIOS for data reduction and resilient workflows. The first one demonstrates data reduction by reducing the grid resolution on-the-fly and applying lossy data compression techniques on data. The second one shows a resilient workflow. If a numerical errors occurs, the new resilient workflow can catch the failed node and exclude it from further simulations without losing too much simulation progress.

6.1 Data reduction

One cheap and easy way to reduce the data written is to re-grid model fields to lower resolution "on the fly". Data reduction using XIOS has been implemented in the Unified Model (UM)[14] to demonstrate this. The method for adding this capability to the UM is relatively simple:

¹³OPH_IMPORTNC operator: http://ophidia.cmcc.it/documentation/users/operators/OPH_IMPORTNC.html

¹⁴OPH_EXPORTNC operator: http://ophidia.cmcc.it/documentation/users/operators/OPH_EXPORTNC.html

1. Define a new global grid. Create arrays containing latitude and longitude grid point centres and arrays containing latitude and longitude grid box boundaries.
2. Decompose a new global grid. Calculate local processor decomposition versions of the arrays calculated in step 1.
3. Send arrays calculated in step 2 to XIOS using the subroutine `xios_set_domain_attr()`
4. Add the new grid information to the XIOS XML file `iodef.xml`, for example:

```
<domain_definition>
  <domain id="um-atmos_regrid" name="regrid" />
</domain_definition>
<grid_definition>
  <grid id="um-atmos_regrid_ufs">
    <domain domain_ref="um-atmos_regrid">
      <interpolate_domain order="2" />
    </domain>
  </grid>
</grid_definition>
```

5. Define output fields on the new grid, for example:

```
<field_definition default_value="-1073741824.0" prec="8">
  <field enabled=".TRUE." grid_ref="um-atmos_grid_t_ufs" id="m01s00i024"
    long_name="SURFACE TEMPERATURE AFTER TIMESTEP" standard_name="surface_temperature"
    unit="K" />
  <field enabled=".TRUE." field_ref="m01s00i024" grid_ref="um-atmos_regrid_ufs"
    id="m01s00i024_regrid" />
  <field enabled=".TRUE." grid_ref="um-atmos_grid_uv_ufs" id="m01s15i212"
    long_name="50 METRE WIND U-COMPONENT B GRID" standard_name="eastward_wind"
    unit="m s-1" />
  <field enabled=".TRUE." field_ref="m01s15i212" grid_ref="um-atmos_regrid_ufs"
    id="m01s15i212_regrid" />
</field_definition>
```

The first example implemented for use in practice is the Octahedral Reduced Gaussian grid. Other grids can also be added using the above steps.

Another essential data reduction method is lossy compression that uses a priori knowledge about useful output precision. The UM's standard output is compressed using a Met Office standard packing system known as WGDOS, which effectively quantises each field to a variable specific precision, using a proprietary format.

The same compression can be achieved using the NetCDF output by XIOS by quantising the data (removing precision) before it gets to the NetCDF layer. If re-gridding is not being used, the quantization can be applied to the data before sending it to XIOS, and data will be compressed with greater efficiency, but when using re-gridding, the data quantization needs to be done after re-gridding and hence needs to be done by XIOS. If XIOS is modified to do this, it will also need to know the quantization level. It can be added to the field metadata in the `field_definition` section of `iodef.xml`. The UM uses a negative integer value `comp_accrcy` stored in the STASHmaster file for every output field. It defines the required accuracy of the data, and the data is quantised using this value as below:

```
scale = 2**(-comp_accrcy)
field = NINT(scale*field)/scale
```

(`comp_accrcy` defines a binary accuracy).

6.2 Ensemble workflow resilience

All ensemble members and XIOS share an MPI communicator, and so the entire infrastructure will fail if one of the members fails due to a numerical (or any other) issue. Our first error handling concept was based on trapping and handling MPI failures. While demonstrators worked fine, in practice, the MPI error handling mechanism has proven to be unreliable. Most current MPI implementations do not fail gracefully enough as once a single MPI process has failed, other processes which communicate with it will eventually deadlock

[10]. Additionally, once one ensemble member had failed, it was found impracticable to allow the remaining members and XIOS to complete.

Instead of MPI error handling, a workflow solution was developed. A typical model workflow involves multiple cycles, consisting of simulation, diagnostics output and checkpoints. Frequent checkpointing allows restarting the entire ensemble (without the failed unit) from the end of the previous cycle without wasting too much effort. In short, if a failure occurs, the simulation restarts from the last checkpoint.

The ensemble analysis system has been developed using the UM to enforce the behaviour, where the CYLC workflow engine controls the UM workflow. It was implemented as a UM CYLC suite, where *suites* control simulations (and ensemble simulations). We used the UM CYLC suite as resilience demonstrator and instructions for generic conversion of an ensemble suite.

The prototype demonstrator workflow is depicted in Figure 6 with generic instructions based on the prototype reproduced in Appendix A.

Figure 6: The ensemble resilience workflow. [C]=cylc [S]=script [P]=python [U]=UM

The basic flow is:

1. Ensemble-member fails from numerical issues. The UM can trap these two ways: either with “NaN trap”, i.e. (`var != var`) in a Fortran `if`-block, or by the exception handler C routines which allow a call to arbitrary routines if an exception (SIGFPE) is generated.
2. If either of the above is triggered, write details of the failure to file and allow model to fail as usual, either via `MPI_abort()` or the exception signal. It is required to a) ensure all MPI processes are destroyed in a controlled way, and b) the model fails to consistent with CYLC expects expectations.
3. On model failure, the CYLC `err-script` option runs a script that checks the failure file to see if the model failed due to numerical issues. If so, use the “CYLC message” to signal the CYLC server on PUMA if that is the case.
4. On PUMA (the system on which the CYLC controller runs), on receipt of the failure message, run a script, which contains the following command line:

```
rose suite-run -C $HOME/roses/$SUITEID -S BADENSEMBLE=$BADENSEMBLE --run=reload
```

where `BADENSEMBLE` is the ensemble number of the failed member. It re-processes the `suite.rc`, overriding the null value of `BADENSEMBLE` in the `rose-suite.conf` file.

5. A non-null `BADENSEMBLE` is detected as part of the `jinja` processing of the `suite.rc`, and passed as an environment variable to the model submission on ARCHER2 when the current cycle is `tr`-triggered.
6. In the `suite.rc`, the `execution retry` option re-triggers the current cycle after a short delay if it has failed for any reason. This is only done once to avoid an infinite loop if the model has failed on ARCHER2 for other reasons.
7. `BADENSEMBLE` is used by the UM drivers system, which builds the `srun` option argument list, to omit the bad ensemble member when configuring the ensembles and XIOS for `srun`. Therefore the re-triggered ensemble runs on fewer nodes.
8. The ensemble is run without the bad member. At run-time, the ensemble "axis" is indexed (the member indexes are 0,1,2...) without the missing member. All over members retain their previous index to ensure consistency with previous cycles.
9. The configuration persists in ignoring the bad ensemble on all subsequent resubmissions.

A demonstrator illustrates the workflow. In a run of a three-member ensemble, each member obtains a different solar constant parameter. Two of them are set to physically possible values (member 0 and member 2), and one is set to a ridiculous value to ensure that the ensemble member crashes. The output from the three members and the ensemble mean output is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Demonstrator output. Member 1 from a three member ensemble has crashed, but execution has continued and the ensemble mean output has been produced.

7 Sustainability

Any software development needs to have a strategy for sustainability, otherwise many potential users may consider that the cost of utilising that code (e.g. development and/or porting of new or existing workflows coupled with the risk of having to unpick it if the software is not maintained) would exceed the benefits.

There are four components to a sustainable software strategy:

1. Develop for maintainability: Document, Test. Open software and open development processes.
2. Grow the user community, including commercial providers.
3. Recognise maintenance costs and identify and/or create appropriate income sources.
4. Learning lessons from the work undertaken.

This document demonstrates the ESDM engagement with the first requirement.

Growing the user community is more difficult. We expect that the XIOS/ESEDM demonstrator project within WP1 (Cutting Edge Resolution in Earth system modelling) and the appliances of WP4 task 7 (Industry proof of concept), all expected by end of 2022, will show the advantages of using the ESDM to a larger community. We discuss further plans for growing the use community in section 10.

Currently the ESDM maintenance is funded by ESiWACE, and bids to both German and UK funding sources are either expected or underway. In addition, we are looking at opportunities to embed the ESDM in longer term sustained model infrastructure funding as part of the European Network for Earth System Modelling - but that will depend not only on growing the user community, but also on the sustainability of that infrastructure itself.

The possibility for ongoing research funding depends on the fit to national and European strategies, which we discuss next.

8 How this deliverable contributes to the European HPC strategies

Europe is aiming for an exascale platform in the near future. It is well known that I/O middleware will be necessary to make the best use of such platforms, e.g. I/O middleware is one of the “cross cutting software requirements” of the UK exascale software programme ExCALIBUR. To that end, then the ESDM is one key piece of software necessary to meet European computing objectives.

Ensemble data analysis and the ESDM integration with visualisation (WP, Data Post-Processing, Analytics and Visualisation) are also crucial steps towards enhancing the ability for "in-flight" analysis of data, reducing the need to write it to storage.

The exact shape of EuroHPC funding for software support is yet to be determined, but we expect opportunities there. The importance of solutions to I/O performance is also recognised by national research funding bodies as evidenced by the ExCALIBUR project already identified above. Similarly, in Germany the importance of data-intensive science is being recognised with structural changes expected to lead to funding opportunities (for instance, the German science council, Wissenschaftsrat, has lately released a position paper ¹⁵ that indicates the need to build competence and software in handling large scale data). These national projects and their successors may also provide a route to further ESDM developments.

9 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

For most of the ESDM work, no changes or special difficulties beyond those described in the text were encountered, but the original plan to use MPI error handling for ensemble analysis was found to be unreliable

¹⁵<https://www.wissenschaftsrat.de/download/2020/8667-20.pdf>

as discussed in section 6.2, and so the workflow solution for ensemble resilience was developed.

9.1 Lessons learned

The ESDM is designed to address the problems with very large-scale simulation, and does not give significant benefits when deployed on small I/O problems (where here "small" means typical existing climate model resolutions where node numbers are not large). Early trials with users have shown that the use of the ESDM in such situations leads to disappointment. Education and communication will be key to uptake of the technology as larger problem sizes are encountered. These issues also affect configuration and the created outputs are important for the performance analysis. Therefore, in the long run, we expect that configuration of ESDM is performed by local data centre experts.

10 Dissemination, Engagement and Uptake of Results

10.1 Target audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

X | The general public (PU)

During the next two years our primary objective is to expand the usage of the ESDM *within* the ESiWACE project while promulgating information about what it can do at all available academic venues. Given the current situation with travel, that will be harder than normal, but we will see opportunities for virtual presentations.

10.2 Record of dissemination/engagement activities linked to this deliverable

See table 6.

10.3 Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

None.

References

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Table 6: Record of dissemination / engagement activities linked to this deliverable

Type of activities	Details	Date and location of the event	Type of audience	Zenodo Link	Estimated number of persons reached
Participation to an event other than a conference or workshop	Julian Kunkel, "The Earth-System Data Middleware: An Approach for Heterogeneous Storage Infrastructure", SPPEXA Final Symposium 2019	21-23 October, 2019, Dresden	Germany Scientific Community	https://zenodo.org/deposit/3985434	40
Participation to a conference	Julian Kunkel, "Exploiting Different Storage Types with the Earth-System Data Middleware", Parallel Data Systems Workshop, Supercomputing Conference"	18 Nov, 2019, Denver, USA	Scientific Community	https://zenodo.org/recorder/3992697	80
Participation to a conference	Julian Kunkel, "Smarter Management using Metadata and Workflow Expertise", Birds of a Feather Session: Knowledge Is Power: Unleashing the Potential of Your Archives Through Metadata, Supercomputing"	21 Nov, 2019, Denver, USA	Scientific Community	https://zenodo.org/deposit/3985492	15
Participation to a conference	Julian Kunkel, "Challenges and Approaches for Extreme Data Processing ", EPSRC Centre for Doctoral Training Mathematics of Planet Earth, University of Reading	11 March, 2020, Reading, UK	Scientific Community	https://zenodo.org/recorder/3985422	100
Participation to a conference	Julian Kunkel, "Potential of I/O-Aware Workflows in Climate and Weather ", Supercomputing Frontiers Europe, Virtual/Warsaw Poland	25 March, 2020, Virtual/Warsaw	Scientific Community	https://zenodo.org/recorder/3985162	120
Organisation of a workshop	Julian Kunkel, "Special Interest IO in the UK workshop", University of Reading	23 April, 2020, Virtual/University of Reading	Scientific Community	https://zenodo.org/recorder/3985174	40
Participation to a workshop	Julian Kunkel, "Toward Next Generation Interfaces for Exploiting Workflows", Special Interest IO in the UK workshop, University of Reading	23 April, 2020, Virtual/University of Reading	Scientific Community	https://zenodo.org/recorder/3985174	40
Participation to a workshop	Julian Kunkel, "Data-Centric IO: Potential for Climate/Weather", 6th ENES HPC Workshop	29 May, 2020, Virtual/Hamburg	Scientific Community	https://zenodo.org/recorder/3985143	80
Organisation of a workshop	Julian Kunkel, "HPC-IODC: HPC I/O in the Data Center Workshop"	25 June, 2020, Virtual	Scientific Community	https://hps.vi4io.org/events/2020/iodc	40
Participation to a workshop	Julian Kunkel, "Data Systems at Scale in Climate and Weather: Activities in the ESIWACE Project", HPC IODC workshop	25 June, 2020, Virtual	Scientific Community	https://zenodo.org/recorder/3985157	44

Appendices

A: Ensemble resilience instructions

Ensemble resilience is discussed in section 6.2. The generic instructions for adding ensemble resilience to an existing UM cylc suite is included here to aid in the construction of similar instructions for ensembles using other model infrastructures.

To convert a standard ensemble suite into a resilient one, the following steps are required. u-cb749 is an example of this.

You first to find a working ensemble suite. u-bj899_vn11.4_t3068 for example. All scripts are in /home/simon/ensembles

The suite should be opened with
 rose edit -M ~jeff/um/vn11.4_xios_output/rose-meta --no-warn version
 to use the correct metadata

Steps:

1) In GUI, add branch fcm:um.x-br/dev/simonwilson/vn11.4_ens_fail_write
 to fcm_make->um_sources

This causes the model to write details of a ensemble member failure to a file.

2) Changes to cylc

2a) Post run check:

Copy check_ensemble.sh to bin and in site/archer2.rc, under [[atmos]] add
 err-script = check_ensemble.sh

2b) Event handler:

Copy process_ensemble.sh to bin and in site/archer2.rc, under [[atmos]] add

```
[[events]]
  handler events = custom
  custom handler = "process_ensemble.sh"
```

2c) Allow one retry after 30 seconds if failure:

In site/archer2.rc under [[atmos]] [[job]] add

```
execution retry delays = PT30S
```

2d) Set up BAD_ENSEMBLE:

In site/archer2.rc

```
{% set APPN = ATM_PPN if ATM_PPN is defined else PPN %}
{% set BAD_ENSEMBLE = BADENSEMBLE if BADENSEMBLE is defined else -1 %} <-new
{% set ATMOS_TASKS = ATM_PROCX*ATM_PROCY+IOS_NPROC %}
```

then

```
{% endif %}
{% if BAD_ENSEMBLE != -1 %} <-new
  {% set NEXEC = NEXEC - 1 %} <-new
{% endif %} <-new
{% set NEXEC = ATMOS_NEXEC %}
```

and

```
ASTART=./recon/atmos.astart
BAD_ENSEMBLE = {{BAD_ENSEMBLE}} <-new
UM_ATM_NPROCX = {{ATM_PROCX}}
```

3) In GUI fcm_make_drivers->drivers_source change to
 /home/simon/branches/drivers_1.3_xios_output

Note:

u-cb749 is configured for three ensembles. The value of the solar constant SC has been changed in app/um/opt/rose-app-ens[012].conf so that

```
ensemble 1 will fail and ensemble 0 will be produce different results.  
Remove  
[namelist:planet_constants]  
to stop this behaviour
```